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Urhobo Marital Values: Ingredient For Sustaining Family Life

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ABSTRACT

Sustaining family life is of paramount important to the growth and development of any nation and Peace, Joy, Progress to the individual homes and the society. However, it appears that such dream is defeated due to instability of several homes, which have led to various vices such as prostitution, cultism, lack of respect, kidnapping, assassination, robbery, oppression, lack of brotherhood, destruction of lives and properties, insubordination, fraudsters, rape, and same sex the above facts gave rise to the topic "Urhobo marital values: Ingredient for sustaining family life. In order to justify the claim, the writer adopts descriptive method. The write up is divided into four subsections, which include: introduction, Urhobo people and their concept of marriage, the Urhobo marital life and family values, and sustainability of family life through Urhobo martial values. The ingredient to sustain family life are: prayer, chastity, forgiveness, goodwill demonstration, counseling, living to one's responsibility, discipline, a time with family members and widow's inheritance. The entire ingredients, when applied to family life management, sustainability will take place. The writer concluded that divorce and lack of peaceful homes, which affects proper coordination of several homes lead to what the society is today, therefore the writer strongly recommend that the application of Urhobo marital values to family life will help to strengthen its wheels, which will translate to a better society.

Keywords: Urhobo martial values, widow's inheritance, family values

INTRODUCTION

Family life cut across all human ethnicity and religious affinities. This is so, because the fate of a given community could be determined through, the character of family members that inhabit it. Thus, responsible family will give rise to peaceful co-existence, positive change and reduction of crime rate to the barest minimum.

It is generally observed that the present day society seems to be devoid of good family life because of lack of proper upbringing of children, and parents to show good examples in the society. To this end, many have shifted the blame on porous family background with the metaphoric word as the Urhobo will put it "Adjomo Ubiaka rode edjee takpe om'e ebere r ugbunu vwo r hurho" which is translated into English equivalent as nobody will deprive a child from growing a protruding teeth provided such has enough lips to cover it. That could be interpreted as whatever one does he/she would be responsible for it.

Those who held to the above ideology and philosophy undermine its effects on the home, church and the society at large. Even though one is responsible for his/her action either good or bad, it spreads to others. The effect is what surfaced in the society today such as kidnapping, robbery, teenage prostitution, lack of respect, terrorism, cultism, corruption and many others. In that regard the writer is advocating that the application of Urhobo marital values: Ingredient for sustaining family life will go a long way to reduce it.

On that note, the writer will look at the Urhobo people and their concept of marriage, the Urhobo marital values and family life, and then sustainability of family life through marital values before conclusion.

Urhobo People and their Concept of Marriage

The Urhobo as an ethnic group are found mainly in Delta State of Nigeria and constitute the largest of all the people's group in the state. They spread over nine Local Government Areas, which includes: Ethiope East, Ethiope West, Okpe, Ughelli South, Ughelli North, Sapele, Udu, Uvwie and part of Warri South. According to Eriwo (2003) as for their neighbours, they have the Bini to the North, the Ijo to the South, the Ukwani to the East, and the Iteskiri to the West

The Urhobo people have many cultural values, which they cherished because of their contribution to the wellbeing of man, home, and the society. These include: Brotherhood, Morality, Economic, Aesthetic, Marital values and so on.

The concept of marriage in Urhobo land is not traceable to any origin like the Biblical concept of marriage as ordained institution by God. God said, "Let us make man in our image, in our likeness. So God created man in His own image, created them male and female" (Gen 1:26-27). He also said, "And the two shall become one flesh" (2:24).

The Urhobo people seem to be consciously aware of the need to get married in order to have children who will bear their names. Thus it will make their names not to be forgotten in the family lineage and in the community as a whole. Other reasons cut across African culture as noted by Oyedele (2012) that: to show that the man is potent, for social reputation and it is also believed that a wife can bring good or bad luck to her husband. If after marriage the husband becomes rich, the woman is good, because she has brought prosperity to her husband. On the other hand, if things are not all right with the husband, the cause is attributed to the woman.

That is one of the reasons in Urhobo land, when elders prayed for the younger ones, they would say "Oma mo aye te we Obo eye Oshare" meaning "may you marry to a good husband or a good wife as the case may be for young men. For they are aware that behind every successful man or woman, there is a wife or husband. On that note the issue of marriage among the Uthobo is handled with seriousness. One of the reasons is that it is the continuation of family lineage.

Lois (2001) is of the same view as related to other African culture. To him, "it is a sin not to do so, because it is a refusal to continue on the life of the family." Again, in line with Imasogie (2008) that "common to all is the fact that marriage is not so much seen as a Union of two individuals but it is a union of two families or ethnic groups if the marriage is exogamic." That is a marriage between members of different ethnic groups.

As a result, the Urhobo look forward to unite with a good family, when it comes to marriage. That is why thorough investigation is carried out by both families to minimize the chance of luck, for the choice of one's spouse without secret investigation could lead to a painful experience of either the wife or the husband including the affected family. Thus, invariably, it brings shame and stigmatization to the family. In other words, many people within the locality may not associate with such family. That is why. In Urhobo the would-be-wife's parents or the parents of the would-be-husband do not give immediate positive response when marriage proposal is made. After proper investigation, especially through the Usuopha, that is the middle man who knows about the history and character of the intended couple along with their family's background would certified before positive response could, be given, if not, one should expect negative response;

The above practice, cut across African culture as noted by Kore (2002) that "the union of a man and woman is usually by parental choice and arrangement based upon the reputation and background of the families concerned." However, some individual among the Urhobo single handedly, introduced their would be wives or husbands to their parents. In such situation, the parent would say Ubiurhe r'o mo nya vwi rhe, oye vwo kwumurhe abo ke, meaning a stick presented by a child would be used to prepare a bow

and arrow for him. In that case, most parents do not have much contribution on the choice of spouse however, in such act, its consequences are not shared. It is husband/wife borne by the one who introduces his/her husband/wife to his/her parents.

Beside the consequences, such method destroyed the value placed on virginity, which is not limited to the Urhobo but cut across Nigerian peoples groups as observed by Isiramen (2014), that "today, the expectation has metamorphosed into sexual attractiveness and physical appearance such that virginity has become unappealing to young men, to the effect that women who want to uphold the tradition of sexual sanctity and dignity before marriage now find it difficult to get married." Another possible reason is compatibility of intended couple, and ability to conceive or have children before informing both parents. Thus, it rapes the marital value of the Urhobo people to some extent because it is not practiced by all in Urhobo land.

After the investigation or the introduction of one's spouse to parents a day would be fixed for the consummation of the marriage according to the tradition.

In line with the Urhobo culture, there are some valuable items needed for the consummation of their marriage though with little variations because of different community's or groups. Generally, the item include one hundred and twenty naira only as dowry, a wrapper (cloth), shirt, hat, walking stick, shoe and money for the clearing of rubber plantation, which is negotiable with the bride father and as for the mother of the bride according to Felicia Omowu as interviewed by the writer, that a wrapper (cloth), head tile, shoe, and Igho rugberhare (money paid for waist, which her mother used to warm herself after delivery), it is also negotiable. Others are, family youth money and drink, three bags of salt with either one thousand naira or two thousand naira to support each. Those three bags of salt are distributed to family ladies, family wives, and the maternal side of the bride respectively.

Furthermore, one twenty litres of native gin (ogogoro) for her father, and four litres for her maternal side. Then, item for the preparation of oil soup, which is eatable by both families, presentation of drinks and kolanuts with agreeable amount of money, that will be doubled by the groom in return, and supported by family members, thereafter, the bride family will invite her mother to seek for her consent, followed by the bride and her family's entourage for her final consent before prayers by her father in a joyful mood. Bride family will raise traditional marriage songs suchs as

Omiovwo vwerhe yoo, je omiovwo vwerha 2x

Ibaba rie phie

Omiovwo vwerhe yoo, je omiovwo vwerha

Ibaba rie phie

Omiovwo vwerhe yo-o, e-e je omiovwo vwerha

Emoribaba omiovwo vwerha ehe-hee

It means that though parents don't sleep, yet it is sweet and given birth to children is good though parents don't sleep, yet it is sweet.

Another is:

Ehe-e ineno avwohwo phopho k era mwa 2x

Ekpako na gheneta a vwohwo phopho

Ke r'amwa: ehe e inene avwohwo

Phopho ker'a mwa Che-e, Che-e ineno avwohwo

Phopho ke r' a mwa Che-e

It simply means that it is true one can protects himself or herself with human being like cloth. The elders truly says: It is true that one protects himself or herself with human being like cloth yes it is true.

More so, Omini Omini Ominio-o, Omini 2x

Omavwerhovwe avware vwohworo omini - O

Celebration! Celebration!! Celebration!!!

It is happiness that makes us to celebrate.

While those songs are going on, the groom and his family in mood of joy will spray money to the bride family before *ebreki ri ine* (closing of songs) with a bottle of gin and money to support it, then couple will dance to the admiration of all invited guests. Before then, there is a negotiable amount for the excursion of the bride by her family to her husband.

Infact, it is a day of joy for both families and well-wishers. However, the interaction of Christianity with the Urhobo culture, other rites such as circumcision and slitting the throat of a he-goat so that its blood would be poured over the couples leg as they remain standing on the door way of the groom house or family compound and also touching their forehead with its blood as a mark of initiation of the marriage into the family ancestral cult so that the wife will be faithful to her husband and also win respect by all who knew her, appear to have been abandoned. This is happening today as observed by the writer in most cases after the bride prize ceremony, couple moved straight to the church for wedding or church blessing. Thus, it is an effect of Christianity on Urhobo cherished marriage culture

The Urhobo Marital Values and Family Life

Culturally, the Urhobo men like other men in African societies are permitted to marry more than one wife according to the ability of such individuals. That is the customary system of marriage among the Urhobo. This is in affirmative with the view of Odje (2011), that the customary system of marriage among the Urhobo is polygamy, which permits plurality of wives at the same time." This does not mean that those who got married to one wife are not regarded as responsible men in the community. It depends on one's interest and man enough to care for multiple wives and children. However, on the part of married women among the Urhobo, are expected to be faithful to their husbands otherwise the ancestors would either inflict them, the child or the husband with sickness that defers any treatment until the woman confessed. However, there are some married women who kept mute and in most cases the end result is death.

In Urhobo culture, the ancestors are believed to be guardians of morality and have powers to punish offenders. That act is similar to the belief of Tiv people about their ancestors. According to Gbenda (2005) "Tiv ancestors are guardians of morality and have powers to punish offenders using Akombo (inflicting the person with disease)." As such the Urhobo married women are always afraid to cheat on their husbands. From the above an average Urhobo man valued many wives, and their fidelities. The fidelity of married women is also valued in some other culture such as the Yoruba people. According to Ayantayo (2009), that in traditional Yoruba society, some husbands out of founded or unfounded suspicion, usually place *Magun* on their wives on the ground that they are promiscuous." *Magun* is a magic, which disgraces an adulterous man with another man's wife either by gluing together or struck the man to death in the act. The action is to promote fidelity among married women. Thus, it is one of the martial values that cut across some cultures in Nigeria.

Another marital value in Urhobo land is centered on children. A marriage without a child is not a good one. It could lead to separation of husband and wife, if they desire. In the same vein, parents may also pressurize them to do so, or some family members of the husband to the wife will advise their son to marry an additionally wife, however if it was the marriage under the ACT, the husband in most cases would be advised to have a secret wife who would live in a place so that the first wife will not know until death do them part. In that situation, the Urhobo would say "*Ophie si nu*" meaning "he born and hide the children." This is done in order for the name of their son to be remembered also to increase the family lineage that is the reason why both parents at most two years of their sons or daughters marriage would be expecting the goodnews of a new born child.

The parental involvement in their children marriage does not attest to the family life practiced by the Urhobo alone but also cut across African culture as according to Kunhiyop (2004) that in "African Cultural System, marriage is not just between the husband and wife, it is a relationship that integrates

with other people and relationship with the family and society." In other words the Urhobo practiced extended family relationship. All the nuclear families in a lineage formed a large family.

The large family in one way or the other contributes to the growth of each nuclear family within the lineage. This is actualized through co-operate involvement of representatives, if not all other nuclear family members in any issue that demands their attention. Some of those issues include: marriage, celebration of the birth of a new child, burial ceremony, ancestral worship, family meetings, dispute between family members or other people. Such involvement enhance the unity of all within the lineage. Thus in Urhobo land, the union of extended family strengthened each nuclear family member. That is why divorce is not easy in Urhobo culture.

Sustainability of Family Life through Marital Values

Ron (1999) on sustaining family life, internet sources revealed what it takes to keep a family together. Ron advocated the following for sustaining family life:

1. Family prayer: The family that prays together stays together
2. Chastity: all lack of chastity effectively destroys family life
3. Adultery and incest ravage the foundation of family.
4. Forgiveness: we must learn to live graciously in a situation within, which life will not be fair, our feelings will often be bruised, our needs will often be neglected, and others will constantly disappoint us even as we disappoint them. When we forgive, when we live beyond our hurts, God can enter our lives in a way that approximates what happened at the resurrection. Forgiveness is the force that rolls back the stone.

From the above, Ron approached family life from Christian perspectives. The writer agree with him to some extent as it relates to the culture of the Urhobo people. On prayer aspect, it is said in the language of the people where the husband or the father of the home will pray for his wife, and all the children in the home with local gin in his hand. The prayer is directed to the ancestors, divinities of the land, and to the Supreme Being. This act makes the family to be closer together and stays together.

On forgiveness, it is not based on a given deity but for the sake of the living especially the children. On that note the Urhobo adult person would say *Ema eroro awo kpa troro vre*: meaning, when one thinks about children, he/she forgives and forgets. Thus, it is another factor that sustains the family.

More so, on the area of Chastity, in Urhobo culture, the wife is required to be faithful while the man is the husband of all but it does not mean that the man should commit adultery. However, he is free to marry many wives besides concubines. Even some married women who want to use it to strengthen their marriages would woo ladies of their choice to sleep with their husbands or for them to marry them as their wives.

In addition to the above factors, others include the following: Goodwill demonstration, Counseling. Living to ones responsibility, discipline, a time with family and widow inheritance. The Urhobo people demonstrate goodwill in kind, and cash. This act could come from either of the couple, kinsmen and those around them. It brings joy and sense of belonging to the family members.

Again, on counseling, those kinsmen who have experience in marital issues are always available to counsel others when necessary. This is to avoid prolong malice, which may lead to divorce or such home may know no peace until issues are resolved. In Urhobo land such counselors patch up quarrels to sustain the home.

More so, living to ones responsibility keeps home together. In Urhobo culture, the husband is expected to provide for the family by empowering his wives either through farmland or given some money to embark on businesses of their choice. In spite of that, some men also give out feeding allowances, which the wives may add to, when it is not enough. Besides that, the husband is expected to perform his conjugal rights with his wives. This is the reason why most men in Urhobo drink traditional herbal medicine to strengthen their manhood especially those who experience weak erection. Thus, in Urhobo land, it is

understood that the more one has sex with his wives, the easier they settle their differences and glue together.

Furthermore, on discipline it is not limited to the parents alone and whoever that commits grievous offense either by the man or the woman, the one offended may summon his or her partner to the family council for adjudications. When such individual is found guilty, he or she would be made to pay a fine, which serve as deterrent to others. As for the children, parents don't spare the rod. It could be inform of words or a broom to reprimand such child. All these is to sustain the home.

More still, is for parents to have time with their children and with one another. It increases the act of love, and to have fun together through indoor game or folklores. In this process, children are taught about norms and values of the people. Children are also taught on how to respect parents, elders, obedient, prudent, and all good virtues that would better their lives.

Finally, widow inheritance is a practice that cut across Urhobo nation. It is practiced when the husband dies. After the burial, the family will converged to share the deceased estate including the number of wives, but if however, the husband married to only one wife, the children will inherit their father's estate after the family members might have taken little as a sign to show family relations. Again, the widow(s) is inherited by the next of kin whether married or not, however the widow's consent is sought. This act will enable the next of kin to care for the family and sustain it.

CONCLUSION

Divorce is on the increase in the society today and many couples are just enduring instead of enjoying. Again, a look at the society, most people have questionable characters, which is traceable to homes devoid of good moral upbringing. To that end, the application of the Urhobo factors of sustaining family life which include: Prayer, chastity, forgiveness, goodwill demonstration, Counseling, Living to one's responsibility, discipline, a time with family members and widow in heritance will bring succor to any questionable home. Thus they are ingredients for sustaining family life.

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